

Repositioning National Universities Commission For Effective Supervision Of University System In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper explored the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective university supervision in Nigeria. The paper used secondary data. The secondary data were collected from both print and online publications. Content analysis was used to analyze the selection of literature for the study. The paper that adequate funding, effective capacity building programme implementation and digitalization of National Universities Commission operation will help to reposition the National Universities Commission for effective university system supervision in Nigeria. Based on this findings, the paper recommends that the federal government should increase the budgetary allocation to the commission. This will enable the commission provide modern infrastructure facilities, ensure effective staff training and ensure digitalization of the commission.

Keywords: National Universities Commission, Supervision, Universities

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Universities Commission was established in 1962 as an advisory agency in the Cabinet Office. However, in 1974, it became a statutory body and the first Executive Secretary, in the person of Prof. Jibril Aminu, was then appointed. The National Universities Commission (NUC) is a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education (FME). The Commission has a Governing Council. Over the years, the Commission has transformed from a small office in the cabinet office to an important agent of government in the area of development and management of university education in Nigeria (NUC, 2024; Ogunode & Ukozor, 2024).

Interestingly, Bisong, Asemota, & Edinoh,(2025) noted that from a humble background of 5 universities at its inception in 1962, NUC presently superintends over 298 Nigerian Universities (72 Federal Universities, 67 State Universities, and 159 Private Universities), 4 Inter-university Centers, 104 Affiliate Institutions and the emerging 19 Dual Mode Federal Colleges of Education (Bisong, J. N, 2025). The Commission has thirteen Directorates namely; i, Directorate of Academic Planning (DAP); ii. Directorate of Inspection and Monitoring (DIM); iii. Directorate of Human Resource (DHR); iv. Directorate of Student (DoS); v. Directorate of Research, Innovations and Information Technology (DRIIT); vi. Directorate of Executive Secretary's Office (DESO); vii. Directorate of Accreditation (DA); viii. Directorate for the Establishment of Private Universities (DEPU); ix. Directorate of Skills Development and Entrepreneurship (DSDE); x. Directorate of Open, Distance and e-Learning (DODEL); xi.

Directorate of Finance and Accounts (DFA); xii. Directorate of Special Projects (DSP); and Directorate of Public Administration (DPA).

The National Universities Commission, as the apex body for overseeing university education in Nigeria, plays a crucial role in the orderly development of the Nigerian University System (NUS) for the production of quality graduates and research output relevant to national development in the face of global competitiveness. In doing so, the determination and regulation of benchmark standards and quality is pivotal to its mandate. With the increasing trend towards digitization in various industries, it is important to assess the potential impact of digitalization on the Commission vis-à-vis its associated Universities. This paper explores the role of digitization in the Nigerian education system, specifically on the National Universities Commission. Thus, the aim of this research is to explore the import of digitalizing the National Universities Commission in Nigeria (Bisong, et al 2025).

The functions of NUC include: granting approval for all academic programmes in Nigerian universities; granting approval for the establishment of all higher educational institutions offering degree programmes; and ensuring quality assurance, through regular accreditation, of all academic programmes in universities. The NUC has a cardinal role of universities' supervision in Nigeria. This roles required the commission to be up and doing and to be effective in the delivery of its mandate (Bisong, et al 2025). It is based on this that this paper explore the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this paper is hinged on the General System Theory that was developed by David Easton in 1953. The theory was adapted from the natural sciences, especially Biology in the works of Ludwig Von Bertallanty. It found its way into the social sciences through anthropology and sociology. This system theory viewed a system as made up of sub-system of the society. The various parts of work together in the realization of the entire system objectives. The system has an inter-linkages among the various parts. The system have a dynamic interactions between the external environment. The system must work together with every part of the sub-system in order to realize the system goals. The theory can be applied in the study because, the university can be described as a system that is made up of sub-system or different parts. For instance, the university system is made up of a combination of elements: inputs (Funds, facilities, resources, ICT, departments, units), process (management, administration, supervision, department, units, TETFUND, NUC, Ministry of education), outputs (graduate students, knowledge, skills, research out) feedback. All systems and sub-system each of them must be available and relate or interrelate with each other in order to realize the university system goals.

The implication of this theory to this theory is that TETFUND as an external part of the university system must play its roles and functions before the university system will realize its objectives. Every single sub-system or part of the university system must function well and be effective to aid the university system development in Nigeria. Every department and government commission or agencies attach to the university system in Nigeria may have its own sub-goals but these sub-goals of the various commission, agencies and departments tend towards the achievement of the central goals of the entire university system and invariably, if there is a fault in one subsystem or department, it would affect the whole university system in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Literature

2.1 Concept of Effective Supervision

Supervision is an organized programme meant to give direction, guidance and control to an individual, organization, or institution to improve their performance and ensure they are doing the right things. Supervision is carried out in all forms of educational institutions including higher institutions. Higher

institution supervision is more advanced and complex because the institutions are advanced institutions that deal with teaching, researching and provision of community services (Ogunode & Adanna 2022). University supervision according to Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) and Ogunode, et al (2024) is the process of improving the performance of the universities through the provision of professional guidance to school administrators and academics. University supervision is the process of helping universities realize their objectives through the formulation of policies and ensuring the implementation of such policies. Universities supervision deals with ensuring that universities comply with the various policies and directives for the development of the universities. The objectives of university supervision include: realising the objectives of the universities, ensuring the delivery of quality education, guiding the university administrators and managers, helping improve the university system ranking and ensuring quality assurance in the system. The supervision of the Universities in Nigeria takes two forms. The external and the internal supervision. The external is through the National Universities Commission while the internal is through the school administrators.

3.0 METHOD

Exploring the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria is a position paper that adopted a systematic literature review-based method. The method allows to collect and review the related previous literature from various online sources. With the aid of digital platform, the researcher collected secondary information to generate knowledge on this topic from 2015-2025. The position paper followed qualitative narrative design method. The researcher has visited different online sites to collect the previous literature and analyze the literatures on the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria. The previous findings are critically analyzed and presented in different themes on strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria (Adapted from Ogunode, 2025d).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion

This output of the literatures on the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria presents an in-depth study and result that can infer conclusion on the topic. The study includes; online publication; conference paper, journals sorted from reputable international journals such as CEON, Elsevier, Hindawi, JSTOR, IEEE, Learn Techlib, SAGE, Nebraska and Springer.

Exclusion

Also, the literature review excludes information from edited books, preprints, monographs, information below 2015 and book chapters (Adapted from Ogunode, 2025d).

4.0 Result and Discussion Factors that enhances Repositioning of National Universities Commission for Effective Supervision

Funding

Adequate funding of national universities commission in Nigeria will help to reposition the commission to be more effective in its mandate and implementation of its policies on the universities. Adequate funding is critical for the development of any public institution. Adequate funding is the key to the achievement of the institution's goals. Adequate funding is the life wire of any organization (Ogunode, Ukozor, & Ayoko, 2023). No meaningful impact institutions can attain without adequate funding. Studies have shown that public institutions exceed their mandate when they are adequately funded by the government (Ayuba, 2015). Ogunode et al (2023) noted that it has been observed that public institutions in Nigeria are underfunded and this has affected the performance of the institutions. Boards, agencies and commissions like the National universities commission are not exempted from the problem of poor

funding. Poor budgetary allocation to a public institution like the National universities commission has impacted negatively the discharge of their constitutional functions. The poor funding of public establishments has limited their expansion in terms of service delivery. For instance, the former Executive Secretary of National Universities Commission while defending the 2019 budget of the commission observed that NUC's budget receipt from its capital and overhead allocations had been quite low, with the performance based on the releases put at 50 percent for Overhead Costs and the Personnel Costs at 72 percent up-to-date since the salaries payment comes through the Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System IPPIS), (National Universities Commission 2020; National Universities Commission 2020). Akpan, (2014) recommended for increment in the budgetary allocation to the commission. This will aid the commission to improve their service delivery and implement their programme as planned. An improvement and effectiveness of the national universities commission is also an improvement and effectiveness of the universities under the commission. Akpan, and Etor, (2016) concluded that the availability of funds is very important in the actualization of the goals and programmes of the National Universities Commission. The provision of adequate funds for the commission will enable them to carry out its mandate. The adequate funding of the National Universities Commission will aid the development of infrastructure. More funding will help the National Universities Commission in providing more facilities such as more furnished offices, ICT facilities, libraries and instructional materials. Available facilities will also be provided based on modern development while obsolete facilities will be discarded. This means that the higher the level of funding, the more the infrastructures that will be provided for the execution of the commission' programme for the universities.

Effective capacity building implementation

Another critical factor that will help to reposition the National Universities Commission is the provision of effective capacity programme. Capacity building according to Ibrahim, Junaidu, Muhammad and Isah, (2023) is the process of enhancing an individual or organization's capacity to improve their performance to achieve a certain outcome. It basically involves providing the necessary resources and training to individuals or organizations so that they can increase their efficiency and effectiveness. Capacity building according to Maxwell (2024) is a systematic process of developing and strengthening the skills, knowledge, resources, and capabilities of individuals, organisation or communities to achieve their goals and objectives. It involves activities aimed at addressing challenges, improving performance, and adapting to changing circumstances, ensuring effective goal achievement. Capacity building empowers individuals, groups, and organizations to enhance performance, capabilities, and resources for effective problem solving and decision-making, addressing systemic issues, human resources, infrastructure, sustainability, and impact. It involves developing competencies, and policies (Smyth, 2022). Ogunode, and Ukozor (2024) viewed capacity building as the process of improving staff competencies to improve job performance in the institutions Capacity is the training that require systematic development of knowledge, skills and altitude required by a staff to perform adequately on a given tasks in the organization. Ogunode, and Ukozor (2024) noted that staff training is very critical for the success of the National University Commission due to its unique roles of supervision and quality assurance attainment in the universities. Staff training refers to the teaching and learning activities carried on for the primary purpose of helping members of an organization acquire and apply the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes needed by a particular job and organization. The federal government should increase the budgetary allocation of the commission to allow more staff to annually go for training in supervision, quality assurance and university management. Femi (2017) recommended that training and retraining should be given priority in the commission to equip the staff of the commission with modern skills in supervision and programme accreditation (Ogunode, Kasimu, & Sambo, 2023).

Digitalization of National Universities Commission Operation

Digitization of National Universities Commission can help to reposition the commission for more effectiveness in Nigeria. Bisong, Asemota, & Edinoh, (2025) noted that automating processes and tasks in

NUC can bring numerous benefits to institutions such improved operation and service delivery. Digitalizing the NUC can improve efficiency in managing and accessing academic records, synchronizing data between faculties, departments and other stakeholders, and streamlining administrative tasks (Bello, 2025). By digitizing the accreditation process, academic institutions are able to streamline their processes and improve efficiency. This will not only benefit the institutions themselves, but also the students of such institutions who rely on their credentials for future opportunities. With digitalization, the accreditation process and other quality assurance process such as NUC's resource verification visits for programme establishment becomes more transparent and accessible (Bisong, et al 2025). Digitalization of accreditation in NUC and in tertiary institutions in Nigeria will improve and increase efficiency in resource allocation, utilization and optimization. Digitalizing and automating accreditation process will support smooth data collection, analysis and storage for decision making. Streamlining processes of data collection and distribution in accreditation process will lead to reduced costs, increase productivity and improve the speed and accuracy of the processes (Ogunode, et al 2025). Venkatapur *et al.*, (2023) and Olofinkua, Onafowope, Oweikpodor & Obona, (2025) concluded that time efficiency through digitization allows NUC to allocate resources more effectively and administrative staff can focus on analysis and evaluation in lengthy administrative processes. Improving the productivity of the accreditation and other quality assurance teams contribute to the quality of the evaluations carried out. Digitalization has become increasingly important in the management of tertiary institutions and especially in the accreditation process and for improvement in the effectiveness of the quality education (Olaleye & Oyewole, 2016; Olowonefa, & Ogunode, 2021).

4.1 FINDING

The paper revealed that adequate funding, effective capacity building programme implementation and digitalization of National Universities Commission operation will help to reposition the National Universities Commission for effective university system supervision in Nigeria.

4.2 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper explore the strategies to repositioning the National Universities Commission for effective universities supervision in Nigeria. The paper disclosed that adequate funding, effective capacity building programme implementation and digitalization of National Universities Commission operation will help to reposition the National Universities Commission for effective university system supervision in Nigeria. Based on this findings, the paper recommends that the federal government should increase the budgetary allocation to the commission. This will enable the commission provide modern infrastructure facilities, ensure effective staff training and ensure digitalization of the commission.

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